

A Study on Manpower Planning at Solara Active Pharma Science in Cuddalore

Jayasri. N, Balamurugan. S, Thiruselvan. J

MBA Student, Rajiv Gandhi College of Engineering and Technology, Pondicherry, India

ABSTRACT

Manpower planning is the strategy for acquisition, utilization, improvement and preservation of an organization. The success of an organization depends largely on the quantity and quality of its human resources. No organization can be successful in the long run without having the right number and the right jobs at the right time. This study is developed for the main purpose of manpower planning who desired to utilize and improve themselves with the proper planning process in the organization. It involves forecasts of the manpower needs in a future time period so that adequate and timely provisions may be made and meet the needs. This study is processed in Solara Active Pharma Science. This study is discussed about the functions, levels and guidelines for manpower planning. Descriptive research where used in this research and population is 100 sample size is 50. The methodology used in this study is chi-square test to find the association between effectiveness of manpower planning and job satisfaction. The finding of this study shows that the level of manpower planning is moderate and there is association between effectiveness of manpower planning and job satisfaction In Solara Active Pharma Science.

KEYWORDS: Manpower planning, Effectiveness, Planning process and Job satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Beach, Human resource planning is a process of determining and assuming that the organization will have the adequate number of qualified persons, available at the proper times, performing jobs which meet the needs of the enterprise and which provide satisfaction for the individuals involved”.

In the words of Stainer, “Manpower planning is the strategy for the acquisition, utilization, improvement and preservation of an organisation’s human resources. It is aimed at coordinating the requirements for and the availability of different types of employees.

Effective human resource planning process

The effective human resource planning offers the following benefits

1. To carry on its work and to achieve its objectives, every organization requires employees with adequate knowledge, experience and aptitudes. Human resource planning is helpful in selection and training activities. It ensures that adequate number of persons are selected and trained well in advance to fill future job vacancies in the organization. Human resource planning provide the required number and quality of human resources at all times.
2. Human resources planning identifies gap in existing manpower in terms of their quantity and talent. Suitable training and other steps can be taken in time ot fill these gaps. Existing manpower can be developed to fill future vacancies.

How to cite this paper: Jayasri. N | Balamurugan. S | Thiruselvan. J "A Study on Manpower Planning at Solara Active Pharma Science in Cuddalore" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-6, October 2019, pp.558-560, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29165.pdf>

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

3. Human resources planning create awareness about the effective utilization of human resources throughout the organization. It helps to reduce wastage of manpower. It also helps in judging the effectiveness of human resource policies and programs of management.
4. Human resource planning is helpful in effective utilization of technological progress. To meet the challenges of new technology existing employees need to be retained and new employees may be recruited.

Manpower Planning Process

HR department of every company has to constantly keep an eye on the human resources that the company has. With every possible event like change industry dynamics, increase in business requirements, skills required for a particular technology etc, the need for having better resources increases. The process and steps for having manpower planning are as below:

- **Understanding the existing workforce:** The HR department has to thoroughly understand the manpower available with the company. They should examine the background, skill set, qualification, location etc of the entire work force so that they have a good idea regarding the pool of talent which the company has.
- **Forecasting for the future:** With constant changes in business requirements, companies must understand the future trend and which type of employees would be best suited for their organization. Hence, companies must

examine, evaluate and forecast the type of employee workforce they want in the future years

- **Recruitment and selection:** Depending upon the business requirements, manpower planning leads to a much more well thought out recruitment and selection pattern. This totally depends upon the forecasts made and the business requirements. Hence, candidates with better qualification, skill set, experience etc are shortlisted as employees to best suit the future needs.
- **Training the employees:** Employees who are a part of the organization are trained to have the best skills, knowledge and understanding about the current job as well as the future requirements.

All these above mentioned manpower planning steps help organizations become better prepared to adapt to new technology, future industry developments and even to face off with competitors.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

According to Ishwar (1991) state that for HRD, 3 things are important namely (1) way to better adjust the individual to his/her job and the environment, (2) the greatest involvement of the employee in various aspects of his work, (3) the greatest concern for enhancing the capabilities of the individual.

Cascio (1992) narrated that human resource planning can be defined as an effort to anticipate future business and environmental demands on an organization, and to provide the employees to fulfill that business and satisfy those demands.

Boudreau (1993) outlined that human resource planning is the process of collecting and using information on the base of which it can be discussed as the number of resources spent on personnel activities.

Caine (1996) mentioned that it is important for organizations to have the right number of manpower in order to avoid the unwanted situation such as the issue of shortage and excess of manpower.

Dhar (2001) assessed recruitment and promotion policies, merits and competence, performance appraisal and motivation, morale and commitment.

Reilly (2003) defined workforce planning as a process in which an organization attempts to estimate the demand for labor and evaluate the size, nature and source of supply which will be required to meet the demand.

Koubek (2007) stated that personnel planning serves to achieve the goals of the organization by development prediction, setting the targets and realizing arrangements leading to current and future ensure of business tasks with adequate manpower.

Dessler and Varkkey (2009) affirmed that personnel planning embrace all future positions and planning flows from the firm’s strategic plan.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find the effectiveness of manpower planning at SOLARA ACTIVE PHARMA SCIENCE.

2. To find the association between the effectiveness of manpower planning and job satisfaction.
3. To analyze the manpower planning process followed in Solara Active Pharma Science.

IV. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

H_a : There is association between manpower planning and job satisfaction.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the systematic, theoretical analysis of the procedures applied to a field of study (C.R Kothari, 2004). Methodology involves procedures of describing, explaining and predicting phenomena so as to solve a problem; it is the 'how'; the process, or techniques of conducting research. The type of research is descriptive. The total number of population is 100 and the sample size is 50. The data collection is both primary and secondary data. For data analysis the chi-square test were used to find the effectiveness of manpower planning and job satisfaction.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Chart1: The effectiveness of manpower planning

From the above score chart it is found that the average effectiveness of manpower planning is 35 out of total score of 50 which lies in Moderate level. Therefore, the manpower planning at Solara Active Pharma Science in Kudikaadu at CUDDALORE is found to be at moderate level.

Table 1: The chi-square table for the effectiveness of manpower planning and job satisfaction

Manpower Planning Job Satisfaction	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Low	0	9	0	9
Moderate	3	15	0	18
High	15	8	0	23
Total	18	32	0	50

From the above calculation it is found that the chi square value is 16.504 and the p value is 0.002 which is lesser than 0.05. Therefore H₀ is rejected and concluded that there is association between manpower planning and job satisfaction.

VII. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION:

Human resources planning is the process of understanding the needs of the company and making any necessary changes to meet company goals and objectives. This planning is important to the success of the company and factors like Tailor made, appropriate time horizon, adequate organization, top management support, participation, balanced focus.

It is found that the effectiveness of manpower planning in solara active pharma science if in the moderate level at the average of 35 out of the maximum score 70 and also found that there is association between manpower planning and job satisfaction Management should consider employee's opinion in decision making process. Employees should receive instructions from the immediate superior only. Management should take more steps to raise the level of manpower planning. It helps in growth and diversification of business. It plays a vital role in managerial functions such as planning, organizing, directing and controlling. As a result, staffing becomes an important key to all managerial functions.

VIII. REFERENCE:

- [1] S. Seetharaman & B. Venkateswaara Prasad reference book for human resource management. Scitech publications (India) private limited
- [2] Preacher, K. J. (2001, April). Calculation for the chi-square test: An interactive calculation tool for chi-square tests of goodness of fit and independence. Available <http://quantpsy.org>.
- [3] Smith, A. R., & Bartholomew, D. J. (1988). Manpower planning in the United Kingdom: an historical review. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 39(3), 235-248.
- [4] Boruch, R. F, McSweeny, A. J., & Soderstrom, E. J. (1978). Randomized field experiments for program planning, development, and evaluation: *Evaluation Quarterly*, 2(4), 655-695.
- [5] Aggarwala Dharma Vira, 'Manpower, Planning, Selection, Training and Development', Deep and Deep Publications, New Delhi, 1987, Preface.
- [6] Noe, R. A., Hollenbeck, J. R., Gerhart, B., & Wright, P. M. (2017). *Human resource management: Gaining a competitive advantage*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Education.
- [7] Guest, D. E. (1987). Human resource management and industrial relations [1]. *Journal of management Studies*, 24(5), 503-521.
- [8] Armstrong, M. (2006). *A handbook of human resource management practice*. Kogan Page Publishers
- [9] Cascio, W. F. (1992). *Managing human resources: Productivity, quality of work life, profits*. (3rd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [10] Dessler, G. (2001). *Human Resource Management* (7th Ed.). New Delhi: PrenticeHall.
- [11] <https://mail.google.com/mail/u/0/#inbox?projector=1>

